

Process of Submission of Application to the Ethics Committee in Clinical Research

Rehan Rub¹, Maithili Janye², Ritu Tiwari³, Shwetangana Singh⁴, Moksha Ponnamma P G⁵,
Harshal Thakur⁶, and Kuldeep Kumar⁷

*Quality Assurance-Clinical Research, Fortis Healthcare, Gurugram & Fortis Healthcare Research Foundation, Gurugram Haryana¹
Clinical Research, Fortis Hospital, Mumbai & Fortis Healthcare Research Foundation, Gurugram Haryana²
Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh³
Fortis Healthcare Research Foundation, Gurugram Haryana, India^{4,5,6,7}*

Ethics Committee (EC) review is a mandatory prerequisite for initiating clinical research involving human participants. The submission of a research proposal to an EC follows a defined process that ensures adequate scientific validity, participant protection, and regulatory compliance. The paper describes the step-by-step process of submitting an application to the Ethics Committee, explaining essential documents, regulatory requirements, evaluation procedures, and post-approval responsibilities. The discussion integrates principles from ICH-GCP, Indian GCP, and India's New Drugs and Clinical Trials (NDCT) Rules, 2019.

Keywords: Good Clinical Practice (GCP), ethics committee, clinical research, Indian GCP guidelines

Clinical research depends on ethical oversight to safeguard participants' rights, safety, and well-being. Ethics Committees-also known as Institutional Ethics Committees (IECs)-are independent bodies that review, approve, and monitor clinical research proposals (Secretariat, 2016; ICMR, 2017). The process of applying for an EC is highly structured, ensuring compliance with legal, ethical, and scientific standards (ICH-GCP, 2016; Indian GCP, 2001) (Directorate General of Health Services, 2001). A well-prepared

submission reduces delays, strengthens ethical justification, and enhances the overall conduct of research (Emanuel, Wendler, & Grady, 2000).

Purpose of Ethics Committee Submission

The main objective of applying for an EC includes ensuring scientific validity and methodological soundness of the proposed study, protecting participants from unnecessary risks, ensuring that anticipated benefits outweigh potential harms, assessing adequacy of informed consent processes, verifying compliance with national regulations, for example, NDCT Rules, 2019 (India, 2019) and providing transparency regarding funding, compensation, insurance, and investigator qualifications.

Regulatory Framework Governing Ethical Submission

International Guidelines

ICH-GCP E6(R2): Defines responsibilities of sponsors, investigators, and ECs, including essential documents and review processes (Secretariat, 2016).

Declaration of Helsinki (2013): Ethical principles for medical research involving humans (Association, 2013).

B) National Guidelines (India)

Indian GCP Guidelines (2001): Provide operational guidance for ECs and investigators in India ((CDSCO), 2001).

NDCT Rules, 2019: Legally binding regulations governing EC registration, responsibilities, and submission requirements for clinical trials (India, 2019).

Together, these frameworks shape the procedural and ethical expectations for EC submissions.

Pre-Submission Requirements

Before applying, investigators must prepare the full study protocol, including methodology, objectives, eligibility criteria, safety

Author Note

¹Dr. Rehan Rub, Assistant Manager, Quality Assurance-Clinical Research, Fortis Healthcare Gurugram & Fortis Healthcare Research Foundation, Gurugram, Haryana

²Maithili Janye, Assistant Manager, Clinical Research, Fortis Hospital, Mumbai & Fortis Healthcare Research Foundation Gurugram, Haryana

E-mail: maithili.janye@fortishealthcare.com

³Dr. Ritu Tiwari, Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission, Ministry of Health & Family Welfare Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh

E-mail: ritutiwari.ipc@gov.in

⁴Shwetangna, Trainee Clinical Research Associate, Fortis Healthcare Research Foundation, Gurugram, Haryana

E-mail: singhshwetangna@gmail.com;

⁵Moksha Ponnamma PG, Trainee Clinical Research Associate Fortis Healthcare Research Foundation, Gurugram, Haryana

⁶Harshal Thakur, Trainee Clinical Research Associate, Fortis Healthcare Research Foundation, Gurugram, Haryana

⁷Dr. Kuldeep Kumar, Clinical Research Operations In-charge Fortis Healthcare Research Foundation, Gurugram Haryana

E-mail: kuldeep.kumar12@fortishealthcare.com

We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Dr. Rehan Rub, Assistant Manager, Quality Assurance-Clinical Research, Fortis Healthcare Gurugram & Fortis Healthcare

Research Foundation, Gurugram, Haryana

E-mail: rehan.rub@fortishealthcare.com

procedures, and the statistical plan. It must check EC meeting schedules, submission deadlines, and required formats (hard copy vs electronic). Must verify EC registration with the Central Licensing Authority as mandated under NDCT Rules, 2019 (Nair & Ibrahim, 2015). Complete mandatory training, such as Good Clinical Practice (GCP) certification, and obtain institutional permissions, such as Head of Department approval and feasibility assessments ((ICMR) & Department of Health Research (DHR), 2017). Ensure availability of site infrastructure and staff, particularly for drug or device trials regulated study. A complete EC submission dossier typically includes:

Scientific and Study Documents

- Final study protocol with version number and approval date
- Investigator's Brochure (for investigational products) (Secretariat, 2016)
- Case Report Forms or data collection tools and /or eCase Report Form
- Study synopsis or summary sheet ((CDSCO), 2001)

Informed Consent Documentation

- Participant Information Sheet (PIS)
- Informed Consent Form (ICF)
- Assent forms for minors
- Translations into local languages with certification
- Consent Form for Audio-Video Recording based on the type of study
- Pregnancy Follow-up for Information and Informed Consent for Pregnant Participants based on the Type of Study
- Where Applicable Future Research Information and Consent form
- Translations and back Translation certificates for Future research Information and consent form
- Optional Genetic Research Information and Translations and back Translation certificates

These must follow the essential elements described in ICH-GCP and Indian GCP, including risks, benefits, confidentiality, compensation, and voluntariness (Secretariat, 2016; ICMR, 2017).

Investigator and Site Details

- Curriculum vitae (CV) of Principal Investigator (PI) and Co-Investigators
- GCP training certificates
- Medical licenses/registration
- Site feasibility form
- List of available facilities and equipment ((CDSCO), 2001) (India, 2019)

Regulatory and Administrative Documents

- Cover letter
- Insurance and indemnity documents covering research-related injury (India, 2019)
- Funding sources and budget details
- Conflict-of-interest declarations (Emanuel, Wendler, & Grady, 2000)
- Institutional authorisation letters

- CTRI registration plan (for trials requiring registration) (India, 2019)
- Investigator Undertaking by the Principal Investigator
- Declaration of Site Infrastructure where applicable

EC-Specific Requirements

- Completed EC submission form
- Checklist verifying completeness of the dossier (Nair & Ibrahim, 2015).

Submission Process

Mode of Submission

Depending on the EC, applications may be submitted:

In hard-copy format (multiple bound copies)

As electronic submissions via email or online portal (Nair & Ibrahim, 2015)

Based on the Study and Type of Submission few documents' requirements vary for

- Investigator Initiated Study (Non regulated)
- Investigator Study-Funded and Non-regulated study
- Sponsor Regulated Studies
- Academic Studies
 - For Investigator Initiated Study (Non regulated) Scientific and Study Documents required are

Final study protocol with version number and approval date

Case Report Forms or data collection tools

Informed Consent Documentation

Participant Information Sheet (PIS)

Informed Consent Form (ICF)

Assent forms for minors

○ For Investigator Study Funded and Non-regulated study

Scientific and Study Documents required are:

Final study protocol with version number and approval date

Case Report Forms or data collection tools

Informed Consent Documentation

Participant Information Sheet (PIS)

Informed Consent Form (ICF)

Assent forms for minors

Clinical Trial Agreement and Budget document.

Memorandum Of Understanding for collaborator and Govt. sponsored trials (if applicable)

Any additional document(s), as required by Ethics Committee.

○ Sponsor Regulated Studies

Scientific and Study Documents as stated in Pre-Submission Requirements along with Patient Study material Such as:

● Sample Patient card

● Patient Study Guide along with Translation and back Translation certificates

● Translation and back translation certificates in English and Regional Languages

● Guide to Trial Participants

● Thankyou Card for participants

● Global Patient Safety Card

● Global Patient Safety Card Translation and Back translation certificate

- Instructions on Home Administration for Participant & Participant Dosing Record
- Patient Dairy either in Hard Copy Format or eDevice form
- Patient Accrual Method for the Study
- Where applicable - Patient Reported Outcome in questionnaire format along with translation and Back Translation Certificate
- Specimen Collection Procedure for Laboratory Test along with certificate of Translation and back Translation Certificate.
- Patient Posters along with Translation and Back translation certificate -based on the Study Type
- Unblinding Card where applicable
- Instruction for use of Study Drug along with Translation and back translation Certificate
- Clinical Trial Leaflets, Translation and Back Translation Certificates
- Pamphlets and Translation and Back Translation Certificates
- For Academic Studies

Study documents requirements to be fulfilled are

- Study protocol
- Case report Form or data Collection Sheet
- Consent form and Patient Participation Sheet in English and Regional Languages
- Consent Waiver (if applicable)

All the study related documents be submitted at least 2 weeks prior to the meeting for consideration in the Ethics Committee meeting (except those related to participant safety, which may be submitted any time) and SAE (On-Site) should be submitted as per the timelines stated in SOP for initial and detailed reporting of SAE.

Administrative Screening

The EC secretariat performs an initial screening by receiving, recording, reviewing the EC Submission application form provided with the dossier and EC Submission documents, to check:

- document completeness
- signatures, stamps, and version control
- conformity with EC requirements
- Incomplete applications are returned for correction ((ICMR) & Department of Health Research (DHR), 2017).

EC Secretariat provide one copy of document receipt form and covering letter (stamped on first & last page and initialled) to the applicant within 2 days of receipt of documents. Make the entry in "EC Acknowledgement and approval log and maintain submitted documents in project file

Ethical and Scientific Review

The EC evaluates:

- Scientific design validity, feasibility, methodology
- Risk/benefit analysis justification of risks and mitigation strategies
- Informed consent process clarity and cultural appropriateness
- Safety monitoring mechanisms SAE reporting and DSMB involvement
- Protection of vulnerable groups
- Compensation and insurance arrangements
- Clinical Trial Agreement and Clinical Trial Budget Document.

- Data confidentiality and privacy safeguards (ICMR, 2017; Association, 2013)

EC Meeting and Discussion

The proposal is presented during a full-board EC meeting. The Principal Investigator may be invited for clarification (Nair & Ibrahim, 2015). Queries if any is raised during the Ethics Committee meeting and conveyed to principal Investigator. It is the responsibility of the Investigator to resolve the Queries within the stipulated time period.

Decision Letter

Possible outcomes include:

- Approval
- Approval with modifications
- Deferral for major revisions
- Rejection on scientific or ethical grounds
- The EC provides a written letter documenting reasons and required actions ((ICMR) & Department of Health Research (DHR), 2017)

Following Elements are included in the Ethics Committee Approval letter

- Approval for "Interventional Research Study Approval letter for Initial submission"
- Date of approval of the study: DDMMYYYY
- Reference No:
- Subject
- Details of The Ethics Committee Meeting conducted.
- List of EC Members who attended the EC Meeting and their Details
- Letter mentioning neither PI nor any of the study team members have participated in the voting/decision making procedures of the committee.
- List of Documents submitted for Review and Approval
- IEC decision statement
- Approval valid till
- Policy of the Ethics Committee regarding Reporting of SAE, deviations, and any updates in the study to be timely informed to Ethics Committee to be mentioned
- Annual review report to be submitted within 1 month of the due date, i.e., 11 months from the date of approval).
- Stating that Ethics Committee functions in accordance with national and International Regulatory guidelines regulatory
- Signatory of the Designated person of Ethics Committee
- Ethics Committee Registration Number to be mentioned

Post-Approval Requirements

Once approval is granted, the investigator must comply with periodic progress reports (usually annually), serious adverse event (SAE) reporting within regulatory timelines (as per NDCT Rules), protocol amendments requiring prior EC approval, protocol deviations and violations reported promptly, and safety updates for ongoing clinical trials-final report following study completion (Secretariat, 2016; India, 2019).

These obligations ensure ongoing ethical oversight throughout the study.

Common Pitfalls in Ethics Committee

Submission

They can include missing or incomplete documents, poorly written or overly technical consent forms, a lack of clarity regarding injury compensation, insufficient justification for the inclusion of vulnerable populations, confusing risks, Inadequate safety monitoring or SAE reporting plans, uncertified translations of participant documents, poor version control ((CDSCO), 2001) or mismatched signatures, Poor Communication with the Ethics Committee, delays in Reporting of Adverse events and Serious Adverse Events. Issues with Funding, Challenges with Patient recruitment, Study Design not clear and inconsistent detailing Timely Notification of updates in the study. Awareness of these issues can streamline the approval process.

Conclusion

Applying to the Ethics Committee is a systematic, rigorous, and essential component of clinical research. It ensures scientific integrity, regulatory compliance, and, most importantly, participant safety. By adhering to established guidelines such as ICH-GCP, Indian GCP, and the NDCT Rules (2019) researchers can prepare comprehensive, high-quality submissions that facilitate timely ethical review. Effective communication, meticulous documentation, and moral sensitivity are central to successful EC submission and the overall conduct of responsible clinical research.

Acknowledgments

We would like to express our gratitude to Dr. Kuldeep Kumar, General Manager Clinical Research Fortis Healthcare Research Foundation and Fortis Healthcare Limited and Dr Ritu Tiwari, Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, for their constant guidance during the review of the paper “Process of Submission of Application in the Ethics Committee of Clinical research.”

References

- Central Drugs Standard Control Organisation (CDSCO). *Indian Good Clinical Practice Guidelines*. Government of India, 2001.
- Emanuel, E.J., Wendler, D., & Grady, C. (2000). What makes clinical research ethical? *JAMA*, 283(20), 2701-2711.
- ICH Harmonised Guideline - Integrated Addendum to ICH E6(R1) (2016). *Guideline for Good Clinical Practice E6(R2)*. International Council for Harmonisation.
- ICMR-DHR (2017). *National ethical guidelines for biomedical and health research*. (Relevant sections on EC responsibilities & submissions).
- Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) (2017). *Ethical guidelines for biomedical research on human participants*. New Delhi, 2017.
- Nair, S.C., & Ibrahim, H. (2015). Ethics Committees in India: Past, present, and future perspectives. *Perspectives in Clinical Research*, 6(3), 19-24.
- New Drugs & Clinical Trials Rules (2019). Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India.
- World Medical Association (2013). Declaration of Helsinki: Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects. *JAMA*, 310(20), 2191-2194.

Received December 8, 2025

Revision received December 19, 2025

Accepted December 21, 2025